

Synthesis of Tetrahalomonoaryl Tellurates(IV)

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Complexes containing tetrahalo (*p*-methoxy or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)tellurate anions of the formula $[R_4M]^+[R'TeCl_3X]^-$ ($R=Me, Et, Pr, Bu, Ph$; $M=N, P$; $R'=HOPh, MeOPh$; $X=Cl, Br, I$) have been synthesised by the interaction of organotellurium-trihalides with the corresponding tetra-ammonium-, or -phosphonium halides in non-aqueous solvents, or by halogen exchange reaction between complex anion with alkali metal halides or pseudohalides. The complexes are (1 : 1) electrolyte in non-aqueous solvents and are characterised on the basis of analytical data, conductance, molecular weight determinations and ir spectral data. Their antimicrobial activity has also been examined.

SEVERAL complexes containing $[RTeX_3]^-$ and $[R'TeX_3]^-$ as anions have been reported¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our studies of tetrahalocyclopentane tellurates(IV)⁵ and diaryltetrahalotellurates(IV)⁶, we report the synthesis, characterisation and antimicrobial activity of some new anionic complexes of *p*-MeOPhTeCl₃ and *p*-HOPhTeCl₃.

Experimental

p-Methoxyphenyltellurium trichloride^{7,8} and *p*-hydroxyphenyltellurium trichloride⁸ were prepared by reported procedure. Tetraalkylammonium halides (B.D.H.) were used as such. Molecular weight was determined cryoscopically. Molar conductance of 10⁻³M solution was determined at 25° by Philips conductivity assembly PR-9500. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 177 grating spectrophotometer.

The antimicrobial activity of the compounds were evaluated *in vitro* against five fungi (*Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Sporotrichum schenckii*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*), and five bacteria (*Streptococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*). Two-fold serial dilution method of Srivastava *et al*⁹ was employed for testing the activity. Sabouraud's medium and nutrient broth were used as testing media for fungi and bacteria, respectively. The maximum concentration of the compound tested was 100 µg/ml. All the tests were carried out in duplicate. The fungi were incubated at 28 ± 1° and the bacteria at 37 ± 1°. Incubation period for all the bacteria and the fungi *Candida albicans*, *Sporotrichum schenckii* was 24 hr. It was 48 hr for *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* and 96 hr for *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*.

Ethanol solutions of compounds were used for evaluating the antimicrobial activity. A suitable control, containing the same quantity of ethanol,

was maintained to ascertain the inhibitory effect of the solvent, if any.

Amphotericin β (antifungal) and Penicillin (antibacterial) were used as standards for comparison.

Preparation of complexes :

(i) *p*-Methoxyphenyltellurium trichloride (1.364 g; 4 m mol) or *p*-hydroxyphenyltellurium trichloride (1.308 g; 4 m mol) was refluxed with a solution of the corresponding onium salt (4 m mol) in chloroform/methanol mixture (100 ml) for 4-5 hr. The solution was concentrated and the complex precipitated by addition of excess ethylacetate. It was recrystallised from methanol/ethylacetate.

(ii) In a typical experiment an aqueous solution of KI (0.664 g; 4.0 m mol) was added to a solution of tetraphenylphosphonium-*p*-methoxyphenyltrichlorobromotellurate(IV) (0.76 g; 1 m mol) in 4*N* HCl with constant stirring. The corresponding iodo compound precipitated in quantitative yield which was filtered, washed with water and air dried.

(iii) Tetrabutylammonium-*p*-methoxyphenyltrichloriodotellurate(IV) (0.71 g; 1 m mol) was stirred with silver thiocyanate (0.66 g; 4 m mol) in CHCl₃ (30 ml) for 2 hr and then refluxed for additional 3-4 hr. The precipitated silver salt was removed and the filtrate on concentration gave the corresponding tetrathiocyanato derivative.

Results and Discussion

The replacement of a halogen atom by one of its heavier homologues proceeds easily in aqueous solution of monoaryl tetrahalo (or mixed tetrahalo)-tellurates employing aqueous solution of alkali metal halides. Tetrathiocyanatotellurate is prepared by replacement of halogen in non-aqueous medium with silver thiocyanate.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR MONOARYLTETRAHALOTELLURATES(IV)

Sl. No.	(R ₂ M)(R'TeCl ₂ X)			m.p. °C	Colour	Analysis% : Found (Calcd.)				Conductance Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)	
	R	M	X			Te	halide	C	H			
$R' = p \text{ MeO} - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 -$												
1.	Me	N	Cl	>250	White	27.43(28.31)	30.04(31.46)	29.00	29.31	4.15(4.24)	124.5	230.7(450.6)
2.	Me	N	Br	246	Yellow	25.52(25.77)	37.63(37.61)	25.97(26.68)	3.78(3.86)		97.9	(495.1)
3.	Me	N	I	222	Red	23.24(23.53)	42.45(43.02)	24.45(24.37)	3.47(3.53)		124.2	268.2(542.1)
4.	Et	N	Cl	140-42	White	24.49(25.17)	28.38(27.98)	34.25(35.54)	5.27(5.37)		151.1	(506.7)
5.	Et	N	Br	145-47	Yellow	22.97(23.14)	32.95(33.78)	31.17(32.68)	4.55(4.93)		140.2	(551.2)
6.	Et	N	I	114	Red	20.65(21.32)	36.72(38.99)	30.98(30.11)	4.61(4.54)		135.8	305.1(598.2)
7.	Pr	N	I	110	Red	19.14(19.50)	34.31(35.64)	35.01(34.87)	5.42(5.39)		150.3	(634.3)
8.	Bu	N	Br	132	Yellow	19.22(19.23)	28.47(28.67)	41.40(41.63)	6.45(6.53)		152.3	(663.4)
9.	Bu	N	I	139	Red	17.22(17.96)	31.77(32.83)	37.12(38.88)	6.00(6.10)		135.7	(710.4)
10.	Ph	p	Br	194	Yellow	16.59(16.78)	23.60(24.49)	47.99(48.96)	3.31(3.57)		121.9	(760.3)
$R' = p \text{ HO} - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 -$												
11.	Me	N	Cl	>250	White	29.00(29.22)	31.10(32.47)	27.10(27.50)	3.85(3.92)		146.2	(436.6)
12.	Me	N	Br	>250	Yellow	25.99(26.52)	37.90(38.71)	24.90(24.96)	3.51(3.56)		133.5	(481.1)
13.	Me	N	I	230	Red	23.96(24.16)	42.82(44.16)	21.98(22.74)	3.15(3.24)		147.3	272.8(528.1)
14.	Et	N	Cl	232	White	24.80(25.89)	27.72(28.77)	35.12(34.12)	5.25(5.11)		128.2	(492.7)
15.	Et	N	I	180	Red	21.00(21.84)	40.00(30.42)	28.10(28.78)	4.12(4.31)		137.1	(584.2)
Anionic complexes obtained by exchange reaction												
$R' = p \text{ CH}_3\text{O} - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 -$												
16.	Bu	N	SCN	128	Yellow	16.50(17.98)	30.60(32.74)	43.00(45.70)	6.05(6.10)		154.1	(709.5)
17.	Ph	p	I	167	Red	11.05(11.79)	45.62(46.92)	35.11(34.42)	2.49(2.51)		151.3	535.7(1081.7)
18.	Et	N	I	145	Red	14.60(14.62)	59.00(58.02)	19.12(20.64)	3.07(3.12)		145.7	(872.5)

All the complexes are crystalline solids with sharp melting point. Molar conductance values of $10^{-3}M$ solution lie in the range $121-155 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in acetonitrile suggesting 1:1 electrolytic behaviour of the complexes¹⁰. The observed molecular weight of the compounds (in nitrobenzene) is approximately half of the calculated molecular weight which indicates that the complexes are dissociated into two ions in solution.

Vibrational frequencies associated with the cations are similar to those reported¹¹. Absorptions associated with the various modes of vibration of the thiocyanate group have been identified and indicate an *iso* structure of the thiocyanate group. All three vibrational modes viz., $\nu \text{C}=\text{N}$, $\nu \text{C}=\text{S}$ and δNCS , in the complex $[\text{MeOPhTe}(\text{SCN})_4]^-$ lie at 1970s, 822m and 470w cm^{-1} , respectively. The position of $\nu \text{C}=\text{S}$ at 822 cm^{-1} unequivocally suggests the presence of $\text{Te}-\text{NCX}$ bonding in the complex¹².

An octahedral structure with one lone pair of electrons occupying one of the positions is tentatively assigned for the complex anions $(\text{RTeX}_4)^-$ and is consistent with previously reported results^{3,4}.

Bioassay :

The cyclic ring compound, namely 1-telluracyclohexane-dione system and symmetrical diaryl-tellurium dihalides have been reported to be effective against bacteria¹. Complexes of *p*- MeOPhTeCl_2 are more effective against *S. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* in comparison to the parent organotellurium trichloride whereas activity against *K. pneumoniae*, *E. coli* and *Staph. aureus* decreases on complexation. Activity against all bacteria except *K. pneumoniae* is retarded considerably on complexation in case of *p*- HOPhTeCl_2 .

In the fungicidal study it appears that all the complexes are ineffective against all the microorganisms examined except *T. mentagrophytes*. Nature of R and X does not make significant difference in the activity.

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